

Lengthened Chain Compounds of Sulphur.

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Recently we had occasion to prepare 1 : 4-dithian in quantity by the method described by V. Meyer (*Ber.*, 1886, 19, 3263), namely, by the interaction of dithioethylene glycol and ethylene bromide in presence of sodium ethylate, thus :

According to Meyer the reaction can be so regulated at will that either dithian alone or its polymer will be the product. If a small quantity of alcohol be poured over the sodium mercaptide and the requisite amount of ethylene bromide added all at once without cooling, the polymer is formed with evolution of heat. If, however, fifty times the weight of alcohol be used as diluent and the ethylene bromide be added drop by drop under cooling, the volatile and readily soluble dithian is the sole product. The polymer, when boiled several hours with phenol, is changed into the simpler form.

We have subjected the "polymer" obtained according to the first method to a systematic examination, and have found it to be a mixture of two brominated compounds, one of which had the formula $\text{BrC}_2\text{H}_4(\text{SC}_2\text{H}_4)_{48}\text{Br}$ —a fact which apparently escaped the notice of Meyer. In one instance a dibromide of the formula $\text{Br}\cdot\text{C}_2\text{H}_4(\text{S}\cdot\text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_{40}\cdot\text{Br}$ was also obtained. The reaction appears to be sensitive, so that very slight changes in experimental conditions produce variations in the results obtained.

An attempt to determine the molecular weight of the compound $\text{BrC}_2\text{H}_4(\text{SC}_2\text{H}_4)_{48}\text{Br}$ by its dissolution in ethylene bromide by the ebullioscopic method gave very interesting results. The molecular weight found was about half that required by theory. It was discovered that the apparent anomaly was due to the splitting up of the long-chain dibromide by continued boiling with ethylene bromide according to the following scheme :

The slight deviation from the theoretical molecular weight is easily accounted for by the fact that simultaneously a much simpler compound of formula $\text{BrC}_2\text{H}_4 \cdot (\text{S} \cdot \text{C}_2\text{H}_4)_{12} \cdot \text{Br}$ is formed in small quantities by the further break-up of the resulting molecule, thus :

The above reaction was also studied under slightly modified conditions, namely, with an excess of ethylene bromide. When the latter was added all at once without cooling, three distinct compounds were obtained in three different preparations. They had the formulæ (i) $\text{BrC}_2\text{H}_4(\text{SC}_2\text{H}_4)_{36}\text{Br}$, (ii) $\text{BrC}_2\text{H}_4(\text{SC}_2\text{H}_4)_{32}\text{Br}$, and (iii) $\text{BrC}_2\text{H}_4(\text{SC}_2\text{H}_4)_{48}\text{Br}$ respectively. Compound (i) was obtained when comparatively small quantities of the reactants were used, while (ii) and (iii) were products when larger quantities of the reactants were employed. If the temperature of the reaction is higher, a larger number of molecules coalesce to form the new compound. This explanation receives support from the fact that when the reaction of Meyer modified as above was carried out according to the second method, that is, with cooling, much simpler compounds of formulæ $\text{BrC}_2\text{H}_4(\text{SC}_2\text{H}_4)_{16}\text{Br}$ and $\text{BrC}_2\text{H}_4(\text{SC}_2\text{H}_4)_{10}\text{Br}$ respectively were obtained. It will be noticed, however, that prolonged boiling with ethylene bromide again disintegrates the compound into simpler molecules (*vide supra*). If these brominated compounds are heated at about 10° higher

than their melting points they decompose into dithian and simpler brominated compounds. That the "polymer" described by V. Meyer is not a mere polymeride of dithian is further corroborated by the fact that some compounds obtained by Bennet (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, 121, 2144) which appeared to be polymerides of dithian behave differently from Meyer's so-called "polymer" when heated with phenol.

In all the methods employed dithian was formed in very considerable quantities. In fact, it was always the main product of reaction.

The course of the formation of the brominated derivatives may be represented thus:

This explains the fact that the product *invariably* contains $(n+1)$ C_2H_4 residues and n sulphur atoms, where n is an even integer.

EXPERIMENTAL.

V. Meyer's Method.—One g. of sodium, dissolved in 25 c.c. of alcohol, was added to 2 gms. of dithioethylene glycol and finally at the ordinary temperature all at once 4 g. of ethylene bromide were poured over it. A white amorphous solid mass immediately separated out with great evolution of heat. The product was filtered under suction and washed twice with cold benzene in which dithian is excessively soluble. The filtrate on evaporation yielded an abundant crop of dithian. The residue, insoluble in benzene, was then washed with alcohol and then several times with water and finally triturated in a mortar with water so as to remove the last traces of

sodium bromide. The dried residue was extracted with boiling benzene; the filtrate on cooling gave a very small quantity of a product which could not be obtained sufficiently pure for analysis. The insoluble residue dissolved completely in hot nitrobenzene. The filtrate on cooling deposited a white mass of m. p. 170° which when examined under the microscope proved to be amorphous. (Found: Br=5.96; S=49.95. $\text{BrC}_2\text{H}_4(\text{SC}_2\text{H}_4)_{40}\text{Br}$ requires Br=6.18; S=49.45 per cent.). This preparation was repeated with double the quantities of the reactants and the products separated as above. The compound which was thrown down from nitrobenzene had the m. p. 163° . It dissolved also in molten naphthalene from which it separated out in a crystalline form having the same m. p. (Found: Br=5.30; S=51.76; C=37.76; H=6.87. $\text{BrC}_2\text{H}_4(\text{SC}_2\text{H}_4)_{43}\text{Br}$ requires Br=5.21; S=50.06; C=38.33 and H=6.39 per cent.). This preparation was repeated several times with identical results.

The above compound was found to be soluble in hot ethylene bromide and an attempt was made to determine its molecular weight by the ebullioscopic method. (Found: M. W.=1486. Calc., M. W.=3068). The ethylene bromide solution on cooling gave a product which was filtered and washed with ethylene bromide and alcohol. Its m. p. was 147° . (Found: S=49.01; Br=10.87. $\text{BrC}_2\text{H}_4(\text{SC}_2\text{H}_4)_{24}\text{Br}$ requires S=47.17; Br=9.83 per cent.) The calculated M. W. of the compound is 1628 which fairly agrees with the observed value. The slight deviation is due, no doubt, to the presence of a very small quantity of a simpler compound (m. p. 100°), which is precipitated from the mother-liquor by alcohol. (Found: S=44.65; Br=17.99. $\text{BrC}_2\text{H}_4(\text{SC}_2\text{H}_4)_{12}\text{Br}$ requires S=42.29; Br=17.62 per cent.)

The procedure described above was slightly modified as follows:

(i) Sodium (2.8 g.), dissolved in 80 c.c. of alcohol, was treated with 5.64 g. dithioethylene glycol, the flask being immersed in ice. Ethylene bromide (17.28 g.) was then run in drop by drop with constant shaking. The resulting solid mass was washed with alcohol, benzene and ether and finally with water several times to remove sodium bromide completely. The benzene filtrate on evaporation gave a copious yield of dithian. The insoluble residue was extracted with boiling benzene. The filtrate on cooling deposited an amorphous white solid, m. p. 120° (Found: Br=20.46; S=40.86. $\text{BrC}_2\text{H}_4 \cdot (\text{SC}_2\text{H}_4)_{10} \cdot \text{Br}$ requires Br=20.31; S=40.61 per cent.). The insoluble product was dissolved in hot nitrobenzene from which on cooling a compound of m. p. 162° was precipitated. (Found: Br=14.71; S=46.02. $\text{BrC}_2\text{H}_4 \cdot (\text{SC}_2\text{H}_4)_{16} \cdot \text{Br}$ requires Br=13.93; S=44.6 per cent.).

(ii) To 1.38 g. sodium, dissolved in 20 c.c. alcohol, were added 2.82 g. dithioethylene glycol. Ethylene bromide (8.64 g.) was then added all at once. Heat was developed and a white mass separated, which was filtered, washed with alcohol and then with cold benzene and finally with water. The benzene extract contained a considerable quantity of dithian. The dried residue was treated with boiling benzene. The filtrate on cooling gave a product which shrinks at 122° and melts at 130° . It was, however, obtained in too small a quantity to admit of analysis. The benzene-insoluble mass was taken up with boiling nitrobenzene which on cooling gave a white compound. It shrinks at 145° and melts at 155° . (Found: Br=9.14, 9.31; S=48.55; C=37.48; H=6.30. $\text{BrC}_2\text{H}_4(\text{SC}_2\text{H}_4)_{26} \cdot \text{Br}$ requires Br=9.1; S=47.59; C=37.07; H=6.18 per cent.) This reaction was repeated with four times the weights of the reactants and the products separated as above. In one preparation the product from nitrobenzene had the m. p. $157-59^{\circ}$.

(Found: Br=7·96, 7·86; S=49·76. $\text{BrC}_2\text{H}_4(\text{SC}_2\text{H}_4)_{32}$. Br requires Br=7·60; S=48·58 per cent.) In another preparation a compound of m. p. 163° was isolated. (Found: Br=5·18; S=51·90. $\text{BrC}_2\text{H}_4(\text{SC}_2\text{H}_4)_{48}$. Br requires Br=5·21; S=50·06 per cent.) The compound is, therefore, identical with that of the same m. p., obtained by Meyer's method.

Transformation of the Long-chain Sulphides into 1:4-Dithian by Heat.—The sulphides were kept melted in a test-tube at about 10° above their respective m. p.'s for a few hours. A sublimate (long, transparent needles) was slowly deposited in the cooler part of the tube. It melted at 113° and a mixture of this substance and 1:4-dithian did not depress the m. p.; obviously the product is 1:4-dithian.

Summary and Conclusion.

From the foregoing investigation it is evident that

(i) The main product of interaction of dithioethylene glycol and ethylene bromide is 1:4-dithian.

(ii) V. Meyer's so-called "polymer" of dithian is a mixture of brominated long-chain derivatives, amongst which the compound $\text{BrC}_2\text{H}_4(\text{SC}_2\text{H}_4)_{48}\text{Br}$ is almost always formed under the conditions stated above. This appears to be the first instance of a crystalline organic sulphur compound of such high molecular weight as 3068.

(iii) Whenever any of these compounds is kept heated for several hours above their m. p.'s, dithian (the main product of decomposition) sublimes off and brominated compounds are left behind. In fact, it is not necessary to heat them with phenol for this purpose.